

ON THE SYNTACTIC AND SEMANTIC FUNCTIONS OF INTERJECTORY PARTICLES “-da, -de/-da, -dä” IN TURKMEN AND “-yo” IN JAPANESE

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As they are considered as Altaic languages, both Turkmen and Japanese are languages in SOV (subject-object-verb) order. Most of the sentence members in both languages have a position in a sentence, even though Turkmen is more available for scrambling. However, interjectory particles in both Turkmen and Japanese come to the end of the sentence after predicate. Interjectory particles (Turkmen: ownuk bölegi [1] [2], Japanese: kantō-joshi [間投助詞]) in Turkmen and Japanese don't change the main meaning of sentence; however, they add nuance which makes the expression stronger. Thus, we can say that speaker wants to express himself or herself strongly, or he or she thinks that receiver is not aware of the shared information by speaker.

In Turkmen grammar book [3], interjectory particle -da (-de, -dä) is described by seven functions: 1. Being added to nouns or verbs in present and future tenses, it makes question in speaking language. 2. It makes the expression stronger in the sentence and speaker wants to confirm. 3. Adding to commands, it repeats the request. 4. After an unknown future suffix added to predicate, it strengthens the meaning of disbelief on a future act. 5. It adds indecision or regret feelings to the sentence. 6. It adds surprised feelings to the sentence. 7. It strengthen the meaning of believing in the sentence. In summary, interjectory particle in Turkmen is added to nouns or verbs which are predicates, and it adds strong impression or doubt to the sentence.

In Japanese grammar book [4], interjectory particle -yo can be added to nouns, adjectives and verbs which are predicates at the end of the sentence. -yo can also be used as vocative case suffix in any other position of the sentence or after other particles; however, we will approach only the one which is used after predicates. -yo which comes after predicate strengthens command, prohibition, or any other predicates as in Turkmen. In this article, seven examples in Turkmen will be given for these functions described in Turkmen grammar book, then their Japanese translations will be compared below.

(1) Tm: “Onda goýna eýe bolmaga çykan oglan sen-**dä**?” («Görogly»)
SO SHEEP +DAT. OWNER BE+TO GO OUT+WHO SON YOU(SIN.)+IP.

Jp: “それで羊の主人になりに出かけた息子はあんたかよ?”

Sorede hitsujino şujinni narini dekaketa musukowa antakayo?
SO SHEEP +GEN. OWNER+DAT. BE(N)+DAT. GO OUT+PAST.T. SON+BP
YOU(SIN.)+QM+IP?

Meaning: So the boy who went out to be owner of the sheep is you, right?

As it is seen, “-da, -de/-da, -dä” in Turkmen and “-yo” in Japanese can make questions; however, it is necessary to add question particle -ka in Japanese to sentence.

(2) Tm: “Munuň geňeşini özüň bilýärsiň-**dä**, Görogly!” («Görogly»)
THIS+GEN. ADVICE+3rd.SIN+ACC. SELF+2ND.SIN KNOW+PRS.T.+IP, GÖROGLY!

Jp: このアドバイスを自分は知っているよ、ゴルオグリさん！

Koreno adobaisuo jibunwa şitteiruyo, Goruoguri-san!
THIS+GEN. ADVICE+ACC. SELF+BP KNOW+PRES.T+IP, GÖROGLY!

Meaning: You know its advice yourself, Görogly!

(3) Tm: “Siz maña ýol harjy tapyp beriň-**dä**.” (A. Durdyýew)
YOU I+DAT. WAY EXPENCE+3rd.SIN.PA FIND+ADV. GIVE+2nd.PLU.COM+IP.

Jp: あなたたちは私に旅費を見つけてくれてよ。

Anatataçıwa wataşini ryohio mitsukete kureteyo.
YOU(PLU)+BP I+DAT. TRAVEL EXPENCES+ACC. FIND+ADV. GIVE+COM+IP.

Meaning: You just find me the travel expences!

In (2) and (3), interjectory particles in both languages don't change meaning but strengthen expression.

(4) Tm: “Şolar biziň gapymyzdan garamazlar-**da**.” (H. Derýaýew)
THAT+PLU WE+GEN. DOOR+1st.PLU.PA+ABL. LOOK+NEG.IND.FTR.T.+PLU+IP.

Jp: そいつらは私たちのドアをさえ見ないよ。

Soitsurawa wataşitaçino doao sae minaiyo.
THAT+PLU+BP WE+GEN. DOOR+ACC.+BP SEE/LOOK+NEG.PRE.T.+IP.

Meaning: These will not even look at our door.

In (4), if interjectory particle adds doubt meaning, Japanese needs “sae” binding particle.

(5) Tm: “Wah, Görogly, men ony birinden nesýe alypdym-**da**!” («Görogly»)
EXP., GÖROGLY, I IT+ACC. SOMEONE+ABL. ON CREDIT TAKE/BUY+PAST.T.+IP.

Jp: ゴルオグリよ、私はあれを誰かに掛け売りで買ったんだよ！

Goruoguri-yo, wataşıwa areo darekani kakeuride kattandayo!
GÖROGLY+VOC., I+BP IT+ACC. SOMEONE+ABL. ON CREDIT+INS.
BUY+PAST.T.+COP.+IP.

Meaning: Ah, Görogly, I bought it on credit from someone!

(6) Tm: “Waý-eý, jan dogan, tüýs Selim-**dä**.” (T. Gurbanow)
EXP., DEAR BROTHER, REALLY SELIM+IP.

Jp: ほらほら、兄弟よ、さすがセリムさんだよ。

Hora hora, kyōdai-yo, sasuga Serimu-san dayo.
EXP., BROTHER+VOC., AS EXPECTED SELIM+MR+COP.+IP.

Meaning: Hey, dear brother, as expected, It's Selim!

(7) Tm: “Şony almak meniň bilen-**dä**.” (A. Durdyýew)
THAT+ACC. TAKE/BUY+NOUN I+GEN. TOGETHER+IP.

Jp: それを買うのは私次第なんだよ。

Soreo kaunowa wataşı şidai nandayo.
THAT+ACC. BUY+PRE.T.+NOUN+BP I+DEPEND ON+COP+IP.

Meaning: Buying that depends on me.

As in (5), (6), and (7), interjectory particles in both languages strengthen regret, admiration and/or belief expressions in sentence.

Seeing that interjectory suffixes in both Turkmen and Japanese are added to predicates, we can say both languages are not only same for SOV order, but also similar with their interjectory particle systems. In addition, -da (-de/-dä) and -yo interjectory particles in both languages have semantic similarity that strengthens the expression but doesn't change the main meaning.

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